

Enhancing Soft Proof Accuracy by Advanced Screen Calibration Techniques

Nguyen Thi Khanh Huyen¹, Thi Kieu Nguyen Hoang^{*1}

¹*School of Materials Science and Engineering, Hanoi University of Science and Technology, Hanoi, 100000, Vietnam*

Abstract— This study investigates the calibration of soft proofing screens to improve the accuracy of color representation for offset print sheets. A highly accurate soft proof was created by aligning the white point, black point, and brightness of an LCD with those of the printed sheet. The average color difference (ΔE_{00}) between the soft proof and the actual print was reduced to 2.18, indicating a significant enhancement in color accuracy. This calibration method offers a practical solution for addressing color discrepancies in soft proofing, thus contributing to the advancement of soft proofing technology and its application in the printing industry.

Keywords— Soft proofing, Screen calibration, Color profile, Offset printing

I. INTRODUCTION

Proofs are essential to meet the printer's and customers' color reproduction expectations. The proof acts as a color agreement and a guide for press adjustments during a print run. There are two types of proofs: hard proofs and soft proofs. A hard proof is a physical print from an output device like a digital printer, while a soft proof is an displayed image on a screen.

The demand for soft proofing is on the rise due to its advantages in speed, cost, and flexibility over traditional hardcopy proofing systems. In addition, advances in hardware and color management technology now allow to calibrate displays to accurately predict the color appearance of a printed product. While soft proofing is perfect for modern multinational print supply chains, some challenges hinder widespread adoption. In the study by S.I. Zhanjun and colleagues on the EIZO CG211 LCD screen under standard observation conditions [1], the color difference between the screen and the print (ΔE) ranged from 1.5 to 6 across 32 four-color prints and 20 three-color overprints. The average difference was 3.2. This deviation is significant and noticeable to the naked eye. The authors also noted that the screen edges should not be used for soft proof verification due to significant color discrepancies with the center area. Instead, the area between 1/5 and 3/5 from the center should be used for checking and observing soft proofs. Research by Peng Cheng et al. [2] reported improved accuracy of soft proofs using the SCCA (Substrate Corrected Colorimetric Aims) solution, which adjusts the screen to match the paper color in the soft proofing process. Color discrepancies between soft and hard proofs were attributed to the impact of Optical Brightening Agents (OBA), which alter paper whiteness. Images with thicker ink layers or predominantly yellow tones were less affected by OBA. The study showed that SCCA could enhance color reproduction accuracy in soft proofing when the paper white point is identified under M1 mode.

Similarly, Jinghuan Ge et al. [3] applied SCCA to soft proofing, demonstrating that the average color difference decreased from 5.94 to 2.81 when soft proofs were corrected using SCCA. This method proved beneficial for optimizing soft proofing, especially in predicting printed image colors, thus broadening soft proofing applications. However, SCCA correction is suitable only for standard printing systems where paper color characteristics meet the standards. In another study, Meng Linlin et al. [4] reported the impact of ambient light on soft proofs, using D50 and D65 light sources at five levels, and found that changes in ambient light brightness did not significantly affect visual inspection and evaluation of soft proofs. Under the same light source, color differences varied inconsistently with linear increases in illumination. In

contrast, Aditya Sole [5] indicated that even within the permissible error range of ISO 12646 for ambient light brightness, soft-proof images on the screen and corresponding hard copies in the viewing booth might not display accurately. Thus, the intensity of ambient and viewing booth light can be adjusted (within the tolerance defined by ISO 12646) based on different work requirements.

This study aims to contribute to developing soft proofing technology by calibrating the proofing display based on the color properties of substrates (papers) and inks. This approach addresses color performance discrepancies between the screen and the printed sheet, ultimately enhancing the accuracy of display simulations of printed materials. The investigation used an LCD screen for a specific offset print sample.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

A. Simulated print sheet

A sample print sheet used in the study to test screen simulations is shown in Fig. 1. The sample print sheet includes the IDEAlliance TC1617 color chart for CMYK device profiling and the IDEAlliance ISO 12647-7 target for evaluation of soft proof. Additionally, it features three images with varying tones and saturation levels. A sheetfed offset printer printed the sample on an Ivory-coated 250 g/m² paper. The CIE xyY coordinates of the paper are $x = 0.35$, $y = 0.36$, and $Y = 86$

The color characteristics of the printer system were recorded in a custom profile with high accuracy. The average difference between 1617 colors on the printed sheet and the profile is 1.02.

Fig. 1 A sample print sheet

B. Display characterization

This study used a DELL E2422H monitor for the simulation. The display specifications are presented in Table 1. The ambient lighting utilized a 36W Philips fluorescent lamp with a color temperature near 6500K and a color rendering index exceeding 95%, ensuring excellent uniformity. The ambient color should remain soft and gentle.

Display calibrating and profiling were carried out by a Myro-1 Handheld Spectrophotometer with BasICColor display 6. The calibrated targets are custom-proofing conditions based on the simulated print (see Table 2). The ICC profile of the calibrated display was created and validated from the automatic measurements of a set of 318 RGB values identical to the test set in ISO 14861.

TABLE I
DELL E2422H DISPLAY SPECIFICATIONS

Category	Specification
Screen type	Active matrix-TFT LCD
Panel type	In-Plane Switching
Active area	Horizontal Vertical Area 527.04 mm (20.75in.) 296.46 mm (11.67in.) 1562.46 cm2 (242.18 in.2)
Brightness	250 cd/m ² (typical)
Contrast ratio	1,000 to 1 (typical)
Backlight	LED edge light system
Color depth	16.7 million colors
Color gamut	72% (CIE1931) 83% (CIE1976)

TABLE III
DISPLAY CALIBRATION TARGETS

Category	Target
White Point	The white point of paper (xy coordinates)
Tonal Response	L* (gamma)
White Luminance	The white point of the paper
Black Luminance	The black point of the print

C. Display quality test

Display uniformity was assessed perpendicular to the screen at nine evenly spaced areas, as illustrated in Fig. 2. A spectrophotometer was used to measure CIE XYZ values at three levels of intensity (White, Gray, Dark) in each area. Tone deviations (ΔE_{00}) were determined for each of the eight surrounding areas compared to the central region at each intensity level. Additionally, contrast deviations, defined as the Gray/White luminance ratio, were calculated for each location relative to the central reference. Tolerances are specified in Table 3.

Fig. 2 Regions to be measured for assessing display uniformity

TABLE III
TOLERANCES FOR TONE UNIFORMITY

Tone uniformity	Requirements
Tone deviation (8 regions vs center)	
White (R = G = B = 255)	$\Delta E_{00} \leq 4$
Gray (R = G = B = 128)	$\Delta E_{00} \leq 4$
Dark (R = G = B = 64)	$\Delta E_{00} \leq 4$
Contrast deviation (8 regions vs. center)	
$CIEY_{Gray}/CIEY_{White}$	< 10%

Angular display uniformity was evaluated using the same nine equally spaced regions across the screen but in directions angled from the central observer point, as shown in Fig. 3.

The CIE XYZ values were measured at different angles using the MYIRO-1 spectrophotometer in conjunction with basicColor display software. The device was positioned so that the viewing angle from the measure sensor to the measured screen surface was less than 30 degrees. The values measured in the central region were considered as a reference for calculating deviations in the eight surrounding areas. Contrast uniformity at different viewing angles was assessed by calculating the Gray/White luminance ratio measurements. Permissible errors are listed in Table 4.

Fig. 3 Assessing angular tone variation.

TABLE IVV
TOLERANCES FOR ANGULAR TONE UNIFORMITY

Angular Tone Uniformity	Requirements
Tone deviation (8 regions vs center)	
White (R = G = B = 255)	$\Delta E_{00} \leq 10$
Gray (R = G = B = 128)	$\Delta E_{00} \leq 10$
Dark (R = G = B = 64)	$\Delta E_{00} \leq 10$
Angular Contrast deviation (8 regions vs. center)	
$CIEY_{Gray}/CIEY_{White}$	< 10%

D. Soft proofing evaluation

The measurements were conducted at the center of the display on 84 displayed patches of IDEAlliance ISO 12647-7 Control Wedge 2013 (Fig. 4). These results were then compared to measurements of the printed patches. Table 5 gives the colorimetric requirements that should be attained in terms of computed ΔE_{00} color differences for the set of patches. In addition, the CIEY contrast between the paper white patch and the black patch (CMYK=0,0,0,100) required a value between 0.5 and 2.0.

Fig. 4 Displayed and measured patches of IDEAlliance ISO 12647-7 Control Wedge 2013

E. Color measurement

The solid densities were measured by an X-Rite SpectroDensitometer 504, Inc. Grandville, MI. Device repeatability was 0.01 – 0.02

The CIELAB color coordinates of the printed samples were measured according to ISO 12647-1 standard on an X-Rite DTP22 Color Digital Swatchbook Spectrophotometer under D50 illuminant, 2° observer, 0/45 or 45/0 geometry, white backing.

In CIELAB space (Fig. 3) [6], the lightness value, L^* , varies from 0 (black) to 100 (white). The a^* and b^* coordinates correspond to the green-red and yellow-blue color axis, respectively, where negative values indicate a shift toward green and blue and positive values signify a shift toward red and yellow.

The color difference was calculated by ΔE_{00} , described in detail in [7].

Fig. 5 CIELAB color space (source:[6])

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Display quality

The evaluated tone uniformity of the display is reported in Table 5 and Fig. 6. The tone and contrast values at different positions on the display are different, not more than 4%. These results indicate that the DELL E2422H monitor used in this study has tone uniformity and contrast that meet the conditions for creating a soft proof. The average ΔE_{00} values for White, Gray, and Dark tones in the eight surrounding regions against the central are 2.04, 1.54, and 1.24, respectively. All the ΔE_{00} values are below 10, meeting the requirements for angular tone uniformity as presented in Table 6.

TABLE V
TONE UNIFORMITY OF THE DISPLAY

Region	ΔE_{00}^*		
	White	Gray	Dark
1	1.03	0.59	0.54
2	0.81	0.26	0.50
3	0.96	0.48	0.60
4	0.13	0.41	0.43
6	0.33	0.36	0.59
7	0.73	0.95	0.39
8	0.20	0.31	0.76
9	0.62	0.76	0.86
Average	0.60	0.52	0.58
$\% \leq 4$	100%	100%	100%

Fig. 6 Contrast deviation at positions measured in the perpendicular direction

TABLE VI
ANGULAR TONE UNIFORMITY OF THE DISPLAY

Region	ΔE_{00}^*		
	White	Gray	Dark
1	1.58	0.76	0.86
2	1.90	1.92	1.25
3	3.62	2.91	1.98
4	1.38	0.26	0.58
6	2.78	2.85	1.94
7	2.13	2.31	1.73
8	0.78	0.82	0.93
9	2.11	0.47	0.63
Average	2.04	1.54	1.24
$\% \leq 4$	100%	100%	100%

The measured contrast of nine regions also indicates that the contrast deviation of the eight surrounding positions measured at an oblique angle does not exceed the permissible error range for contrast deviation, which is $\leq 10\%$ (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 Contrast deviation measured at different angled directions from the center.

B. Display color characteristics

The calibration and profile creation results, as reported in the Table, show that the generated profile has high accuracy, with an average Delta E of 0.44 and a maximum deviation of only 0.76. The calibration results indicate that the screen is fully compatible with the printed sheet in terms of white point, black point, and luminance.

TABLE VII
CALIBRATION AND PROFILE ACCURACY OF THE DISPLAY

Category	Target xy	Achieved	Tolerance
White Point	0.35, 0.36	0.3513, 0.3604	Δab 2.0
Tonal Response	L*		
White Luminance	86.03 cd/m ²	86.0 cd/m ²	$\pm 10.0\%$
Black Luminance	0.85 cd/m ²	0.72 cd/m ²	
Contrast		1:990	
		ΔE_{00}	Tolerance
Average		0.44	3.00
Max. grayscale		1.02	3.00
Max. color		0.76	1.00

C. Soft proofing accuracy

When comparing the printed sample sheet and the soft proof sample, the average ΔE_{00} value is 2.18, the maximum ΔE_{00} value is 6.29, and the W/B contrast value is 0.505, all within the required range of evaluation results for soft proofing (Table 8). Only five colors with ΔE_{00} values > 5 , accounting for 6% (Fig. 8). However, the maximum gray ΔE_{00} value is 4.0, while the requirement for the maximum gray ΔE_{00} value is ≤ 3 . This deviation is mainly in a* value difference between the sample sheet and the screen simulation. The a* value of the color measured on the screen is larger than the a* value calculated on the printed sheet, indicating that the screen performance is more red than the color on the printed sheet.

TABLE VIII
DISPLAY CALIBRATION AND PROFILE

Display / Print Comparison	Requirements	Archived
84 CMYK_Sim_Ref patches	Mean $\Delta E_{00} \leq 4$ Max $\Delta E_{00} \leq 6.5$ Composed gray – Max $\Delta E_{00} \leq 3$	Mean $\Delta E_{00} = 2.18$ Max $\Delta E_{00} = 6.29$ Composed gray – Max $\Delta E_{00} = 4.0$
Ratio of W/B contrast	$0.5 \leq (Y_w/Y_b)_{\text{print}} / (Y_w/Y_b)_{\text{display}} \leq 2.0$	$(Y_w/Y_b)_{\text{print}} / (Y_w/Y_b)_{\text{display}} = 0.505$

Fig. 8 CIE Lab value differences between the displayed and printed colors

It can be concluded that the accuracy of the soft proof is significantly higher than in previous studies. The calibration method of aligning the screen according to the color characteristics of specific papers and inks brings efficiency to soft proofing technology.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a soft proof simulating an offset print sheet was successfully created on an LCD screen. The proofing screen was calibrated to match the white point, black point, and brightness of the print sheet. As a result, the color displayed on the screen closely approximated the corresponding color on the printed sheet. This enhancement demonstrates the effectiveness of the calibration method in achieving a more accurate representation of printed colors, thus advancing the technology and reliability of soft proofing in the printing industry.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Zhanjun, W. Jia, and G. Chong, "Research and application on screen soft proofing technology in printing quality control," *Appl. Mech. Mater.*, vol. 262, pp. 263–268, 2013, doi: 10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.262.263.
- [2] P. Cheng, "RIT Digital Institutional Repository Proof-to-Print Match: Effectiveness of Substrate-Corrected Colorimetric Aims in Soft Proofing," Rochester Institute of Technology, 2014.
- [3] J. Ge, E. Fang, and D. Tian, *Research on the Soft Proofing Technology Based on Substrate-Corrected Colorimetric Aims*, vol. 543. Springer Singapore, 2019.
- [4] L. Meng, J. Zhang, and H. Liu, "The research on effect of ambient light on the impact of the soft proofing," *Adv. Mater. Res.*, vol. 174, pp. 60–63, 2011, doi: 10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.174.60.
- [5] A. Sole, "implementing ISO12646 standars for soft proofing in a standardized printing workflow," *Eng. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 1, pp. 221–225, 2010.
- [6] B. C. K. Ly, E. B. Dyer, J. L. Feig, A. L. Chien, and S. Del Bino, "Research Techniques Made Simple: Cutaneous Colorimetry: A Reliable Technique for Objective Skin Color Measurement," *J. Invest. Dermatol.*, vol. 140, no. 1, pp. 3-12.e1, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jid.2019.11.003.
- [7] http://www.brucelindbloom.com/index.html?Eqn_DeltaE_CIE2000.html